

SSAA - EMA

SETTLEMENT OF THE SOUTHEASTERN ALPINE
AREA IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES

D2.1a: Archaeological interpretation of the ALS data. The Bled micro-region

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable 2.1a is an interim airborne LiDAR report developed within a collaboration between WP2.1 (E. Lozić) and WP4.1 (B. Štular, M. Belak, A. Pleterski).

Due to the specific archaeology, geology and geomorphology of the Bled micro-region the archaeological interpretation of airborne LiDAR derived data has been focused on detecting new Late Antiquity Period settlements. As in any airborne LiDAR analysis entire archaeological landscape record must be taken into account.

Over 1000 features has been recorded, 265 of those are potential archaeological features. As the most important result of this analysis a discovery of previously unknown Prehistoric and Late Antiquity Period hillfort settlement on Ribenska gora is to be mentioned.

This report is a base for further work within WP4.1 that will include further intensive site recognition on the Ribenska gora site. The resulting information will be included in the final D2.2 deliverable of the WP2.1.

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1. Introduction

Project's aim is to study of the settlements of the south-eastern Alpine region in the Early Middle Ages (circa 6th – 11th Century). In the first case study we have focused at the Bled micro-region that covers an area of about 80 km². The micro-region is delimited to the east by the confluence of the rivers Sava Bohinjka and Sava Dolinka, with high mountain plateaux of Pokljuka and Mežakla to the west and north, respectively (*Fig. 1*).¹

Archaeological background has been presented and the area of the Bled micro-region has been defined by Andrej Pleterski in his book *The Invisible Slavs*.² This study has been chosen for the project mainly because majority of the sites from the Early Middle Ages in the area have been archeologically investigated.³

Availability of ALS data has enable us to use this important tool for archeological research.⁴

This remote sensing techniques is currently mainly focused on discovering and recording sites and monuments. However, in this project the archaeological interpretation of ALS data for the Bled micro-region has been used primarily as an aid in contextualizing archeological data in their physical environment. This is due to the fact that the early medieval settlements in the Bled micro-region cannot be detected using remote sensing techniques. Key factors are: a. archeological material evidence are simply poorly preserved (wooden structure)⁵; b. the location of the known early medieval settlements are only partially preserved due later interventions⁶; c. most of the sites is assumed to be located at the present villages (Mlino).⁷ Therefore our research approach has been redirected to the Late Antiquity archeological sites. Additional reasons for this methodological choice are that Late Antiquity settlement sites can be recognized on ALS data but also since one of the project's research focuses is to address the question of transition from Late Antique to Early Medieval Period.⁸

Key task for ALS in the Bled micro-region case study was therefore to quest for undiscovered Late Antiquity settlements and possibly Antiquity field systems. ALS data seemed to perfectly suited for this task.

The report presents the results of the GIS-based analysis of ALS data, historical maps and archeological data supported with ground assessment archeological field survey.

¹ Pleterski 2013, 15.

² Pleterski 2013, 11.

³ Pleterski 2013, 12.

⁴ Archeological interpretation of ALS data has already been applied to a selected part of this micro-region by Mlekuž 2017.

⁵ E.g., during excavation (between 1943-1951) of the settlement Pristava the existence of early medieval settlement layer above an older cemetery has not been recognised (Pleterski 2010, 13).

⁶ E.g. Pristava hill, settlement at the Bled Castle Hill (Pleterski 2008, 107-130; Pleterski 2008a, 156-161, Pleterski 2010, 161-176; Knific 2008, 24).

⁷ Pleterski 2013, 97.

⁸ Kokalj, Zaksek, Oštir 2011, 263-273.

2. Methodology

2.1. Processing Lidar data⁹

LiDAR Point cloud classification. Lidar point cloud was reclassified for the purposes of identifying small-scale archaeological features by using LAStools software. The original las. files were re-classified to create two new DTMs specifically for the purposes of archaeological analysis.¹⁰ *Interpolation of DEM.* New gridded datasets (DEMs) were interpolated by using one of the more accurate geostatistical gridding methods – *kriging*. This has been done by using SURFER (Golden Software) program. *DEM visualization.* For the purpose of interpreting results lidar data good practice is suggesting to use different visualization technique. Each technique is suited for specific objectives, the morphology of features of interests, and the local topography.¹¹ Therefore we have used Relief Visualization Toolbox (RVT 1.1) to create different visualizations from high-resolution digital elevation data derived from areal laser scanning.¹² We have visualize 0.5m and 1m digital elevation models (DEM).¹³ Visualization technique used are: *hillshading* (HS), *local dominance* (LD), *sky-view factor* (SVF) and *positive openness* (OPEN-POS). Toolbox output a pair of GeoTiffs per each selected visualization. One file gives precise calculated result (“a picture”) optimized for viewing in non-GIS software (Windows Photo Viewer or Preview). Output file names for visualizations are composed of the input file name and suffixes and processing parameters.¹⁴ Each execution of the program also generates a processing log file per input file, this automatically assembling metadata.¹⁵

2.2 Archeological Interpretation

⁹ Data source: Slovenian Environment Agency (http://gis.arso.gov.si/evode/profile.aspx?id=atlas_voda_Lidar@Arso). Technical report for the lidar data with metadata (lidar sensor, nominal scanning density, nominal swath overlap, flight height, date of data collection and purpose of data collection) is published (Geodetski inštitut Slovenije: *Izvedba laserskega skeniranja Slovenije. Blok 36- tehnično poročilo o izdelavi izdelkov.* – Ljubljana).

¹⁰ The list of processed files: 426_134, 426_135, 426_136, 426_137, 426_138, 426_139, 426_140, 426_141, 426_142; 427_134, 427_135, 427_136, 427_137, 427_138, 427_139, 427_140, 427_141, 427_142; 428_134, 428_135, 428_136, 428_137, 428_138, 428_139, 428_140, 428_141, 428_142; 429_134, 429_135, 429_136, 429_137, 429_138, 429_139, 429_140, 429_141, 429_142; 430_134, 430_135, 430_136, 430_137, 430_138, 430_139, 430_140, 430_141, 430_142; 431_134, 431_131, 431_136, 431_137, 431_138, 431_139, 431_140, 431_141, 431_142; 432_134, 432_135, 432_136, 432_137, 432_138, 432_139, 432_140, 432_141, 432_142; 433_134, 433_135, 433_136, 433_137, 433_138, 433_139, 433_140, 433_141, 433_142; 434_134, 434_135, 434_136, 434_137, 434_138, 434_139, 434_140, 434_141, 434_142; 435_134, 435_135, 435_136, 435_137, 435_138, 435_139, 435_140, 435_141, 435_142; 436_134, 436_135, 436_136, 436_137, 436_138, 436_139, 436_140, 436_141, 436_142; 437_134, 437_135, 437_136, 437_137, 437_138, 437_139, 437_140, 437_141, 437_142.

¹¹ Kokalj *et al.*, 2013, 102–103; Bennett *et al.* 2012.

¹² Zakšek K, Oštir K, Kokalj Ž. 2011.

¹³ <https://iaps.zrc-sazu.si/en/rvt#v>

¹⁴ Files for 0.5m DTM created: Bled_DEM05_HS_A315_H35_8bit.tif; Bled_DEM05_LD_R_M10-20_DI1_A15_OH1.7_8bit.tif; Bled_DEM05_OPEN-POS_R10_D16_NRlow_8bit.tif; Bled_DEM05_SVF_R10_D16_NRlow_8bit.tif.

Files for 1m DTM created: 1m_DTM_HS_A315_H35_8bit.tif; 1m_DTM_OPEN-POS_R10_D32_NRlow_8bit; 1m_DTM_SVF_R10_D32_NRlow_8bit.tif

¹⁵ Kokalj, Žiga, Ralf Hesse. 2017.

In the proper interpretation of remote sensing data it is important to have basic knowledge about local geological setting and geomorphological process. The Bled area has been shaped by glaciers, therefore, remains of last glaciations (drumlins, moraines) are omnipresent and have a pronounced impact on the archaeological interpretation.¹⁶ This region was shaped during the quaternary glaciations when this tectonic basin was covered by ground moraines of the Bohinj glacier as well as by the fluvial sediments which cover the larger part of the Bled plateau.¹⁷ During the glacier's withdrawal smaller moors and marshes were created between the terminal and lateral moraines.¹⁸ For this reason it was not always easy to distinguish between archaeological features and natural geological phenomena (see below, Zone 2&3).

Archeological prospection and interpretation has been severely hindered on alluvial lowland due to the key factors: topography resulting from complex geomorphological process (see below), intensive agriculture (intensive plowing) and modern infrastructure development. Therefore, archeological features are hardly visible (*Fig. 2*).

The work on project has consisted of two phases: desktop nad field assessment.

2.3. Desktop assessment

The archaeological interpretation process starts with a desk-based assessment. It's aim is to identify the archaeological potential of an area using ALS data, previously published research data existing archaeological databases¹⁹, excavation reports²⁰ and historical maps²¹.

Contextual understanding of the Bled area was supported by documentation of modern roads, pathways, river courses and modern buildings and agricultural activity. For this purpose digital (modern) cadastral map (DKM), topographic maps scale 1:5000 and orthophotos were added.²² This is the first step in the interpretation process of the ALS data interpretation. Produced data are combined in a Geographic Information System (GIS) to achieve more comprehensive archaeological interpretation. All the data are georeferenced and subsequently imported into a GIS environment and merged with other sources of information for integral data treatment. The hybrid outcome can be presented on a single image.

Interpretive mapping has been done in ArcGIS 10.3 (Arc Catalog 10.3). For this purpose we have used line as shape file. Features type: Point and Polyline. Spatial Reference: Current coordinate system: Transverse _Mercator_ Projection.

¹⁶ cf. Dragantis et al. 2015, 96-110.

¹⁷ Melnik 1929/1930, 1-39.

¹⁸ Novak & Bavec 2013, 29.

¹⁹ ARKAS (<http://arkas.zrc-sazu.si>), Zbiva v3.08 (<http://zbiva.zrc-sazu.si/>), The Register of Slovene Cultural Heritage <http://rkd.situla.org>. I thank M. Belak for providing, selecting and preparing data.

²⁰ List of excavations reports, see below.

²¹ Franciscan Cadaster (Cadastral units: (*Historical name*; Ref. Code; Ref. Code AP): Ribno (*Reifen*, SI AS 181/L/224; L224), Selo pri Bledu (*Zellach*, SI AS 176/L/L343; L343), Želeče (*Schalkendorf*, SI AS 181/L/L243; L243), Bled (*Veldes*, SI AS 176/L/L317; L 317), Rečica (*Retschitz*, SI AS 176/L/L227; L 227), Zasip (*Asp*, SI AS 181/L/L9; L9), Podhom (*Buchheim*, SI AS 181/L/L22; L 22); Poljšica (Pogelschitsch; SI AS 176/L/L210; L210), Zgornje Gorje (Obergöriach; SI AS 181/L/L179; L179), Višelnica (*Wischelnitz*, SI AS 181/L/L322; L322), Spodnje Gorje (*Untergöriach*; SI AS 181/L/L310; L310), Blejska Dobrava (*Dobrawa*; SI AS 176/L/L35; L35); MAPIRE. Maps: Europe in the XIX. century (with the Third Military Survey) Illyiria (1829-1835) - Second Military Survey of the Habsburg Empire <https://mapire.eu/en/>;

²² Data source: Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning of the Republic of Slovenia.

Ministry of the Environmental and Spatial Planning (<https://www.e-prostor.gov.si/access-to-geodetic-data/ordering-data/>).

In order to make the interpretation process reproducible, selected criteria for interpretation of each individual features has been defined and recorded in geodatabase: number, type, features type, confidence, chronology, chronology confidence, description: short description of feature; interpretation, source of visualization, author, date (please see *attachment 1*). In this particular case study 265 archaeological features were recorded. The features were then grouped into 5 zones spread across the study area, taking in a variety of geomorphological and ground cover conditions (*Fig. 2*). Inspection of the ALS imagery (variety of visualizations), prior to fieldwork, led to the identification of zones of interest for potential ground-check. Features identified included those at known archaeological sites, as well as a number in areas not yet explored. The value of the initial assessment, therefore, was in providing a map of areas where fieldwork would be most profitable, and indications of the general type of remains to be expected (ZRC team meeting 26. Avgust 2019). A booklet of maps showing the visualizations of each zone, with initial interpretations marked as vectors, was made available pdf. and GIS formats. GPS coordinates along likely archaeological features were extracted to facilitate fieldwork planned for summer of 2019. Maps were uploaded on *Avenza Map App*²³ which allowed us to locate and record field data.

2.4. Field Assessment Method

Selected areas were visited in the field to determine whether an archaeological site was present and assess the chronology of any material culture visible on the surface. The survey was undertaken during a two day period. The field activities were organised using ArcGIS® software by Esri²⁴, locations were visited by navigations to them using Google Maps 2019²⁵, and all data (including locations and notes) were collected using Avenza Maps.²⁶ The survey team: dr. Benjamin Štular (ZRC SAZU); dr. Edisa Lozić (Universität Graz, Institut für Antike)
Equipment: car (Citroën Berlingo), laptop (MacBook Pro 13"), tablet (iPad Air 2), camera (Nikon 1 J2), 1m Steel Ranging Pole.

²³ Avenza Maps® *Avenza Maps*. [online] Available at: <https://www.google.com.au/maps> [Accessed 27, Avg. 2019].

²⁴ ESRI 2011. *ArcGIS Desktop*: Release 10.3 Redlands, CA: Environmental Systems Research Institute.

²⁵ Google Maps 2019, *Google Maps*. [online] Available at: <https://www.google.com.au/maps> [Accessed 27, Avg. 2019].

²⁶ Avenza Maps® *Avenza Maps*. [online] Available at: <https://www.google.com.au/maps> [Accessed 27, Avg. 2019].

3. Field Assessment Results

3.1 Zone 1 (Tuesday, 27. 08. 2019)

Description of the traces recorded on ALS. Ribenska gora, Ribno (Fig. 3; 3a).

The site is located on the north-eastern slope of the hill Ribenska gora, approximately 300m west of today village Ribno. The existence of the site has not previously been reported or recognized. The possible settlement presents a typical Late Antiquity settlement layout with small terraces and occupy the area of 2 hectares. On ALS data visualizations it seems that a settlement plan can be recognised (Fig. 3). Sunken road on east side (ID 1) of the hill suggest that this was main communication to and from the settlement. The road seems to have been partially widened in the modern period (ID 2), possible for the usage of (Triassic Dolomit) quarry (ID 13). Numerous small quarry faces are visible along left side of the road (ID 13). Stone chunks also suggest the existence of the probably early modern period quarry (ID 3). On the ALS image the square structure ca. 4m x 4m, perhaps tower (ID 5), is visible at the beginning of the terrace that runs along the eastern edge of the settlement. Small path is passing around the structure along it's eastern edge of the structure small path is passing by (ID 4). Very distinctive and also easily recognisable at the site are terraces on the eastern edge which are facing very steep slope in the direction NW-SE (ID 7, 8, 11, 12).

Approximately length of the terrace is 50m. Above the terrace it is possible to recognise numerous rectangular features which could be recognise as individual buildings (ID 10). On the terraces prehistoric pottery lying on erosion surface and under fallen tree roots (ID 6, ID 9, ID 14).

During ground assessment prehistoric pottery has been discovered. The naturally protected position, placement and morphology of the site and possible mortar could suggest existence of Iron Age and perhaps even Late Antiquity settlement. The existence of the settlement still needs to be verified, for this fieldwork is planned.

To this it should be added that the location of a supposed Late Antiquity settlement on the site Višce adjacent to the Bled castle has been recently confirmed.²⁷ It is worth mentioned that small excavation taking place in the Summer 2019 revealed only a few Late Antiquity shards (less than 3%)²⁸ despite otherwise clear indications – e.g. golden coin and other finds discovered by metal detectors – for Late Antiquity settlement.

3.2 Zone 2 (Tuesday, 27. 08. 2019)

Description of the traces recorded on ALS. Location place name Čisto polje (Fig. 4; 4a).

Main interest in *Zone 2* is the feature that is visible on a surface as a ridge or a possible earthwork running runs across the entire the Čisto polje. The feature goes in straight line in the east-west direction and measures approximately 1.3km in length. It starts near the village Jermanka and ends at the edge of the glaciofluvial Sava River terrace. In the last 100 m it slightly changes direction to the south. The feature's width is between 6m and 10m. For this feature A. Pleterski has assumed a possibility of reminiscent of roman field system. Most clearly feature can be recognised approximately 0.5km south-east of the village Jermanka (ID

²⁷ Knific 2004, 102; Mušič et al. 2018.

²⁸ Information B. Štular based on personal inquest of the pottery.

15). Here the feature was cut by modern path. The feature is easily recognizable on the surface (ID 17-21) despite the intensive ploughing. It is formed by different unconsolidated stone materials that ranges in size from large blocks or boulders to sand and clay. The materials are not stratified and show no sorting or bedding (ID 16). It seems this is geological feature, possible terminal moraines.²⁹

On this area two arcs of terminal moraines of the Bohinj glacier have been preserved. Those between Bled and Radovljica were formed during the melting of the last, i.e. the youngest Pleistocene Bohinj glacier, with traces of its retreat well preserved in the form of two ridges of the frontal moraines near Dobravca.³⁰ However, the feature discussed is straight whereas a typical terminal moraine is U shaped. To further substantiate this interpretation an opinion of geologist (perhaps dr. Matevž Novak) is recommended.

Further 617 low relief round features (4 to 7m radius; high 2-4m) have been recognized on ALS image. The density of the features is particularly high in the area with place name Dobravca, situated between Sava River's terrace on the east and city of Bled. Numerous features can also be recognized on the other side of Sava Dolinka in the area between Radovljica and Lesce (*Fig. 2*). In this case detecting and documenting archeological features with remote sensing presented very difficult challenge.

As we have mentioned the Bled area has been shaped by glaciers, therefore, remains of last glaciations (moraines) are omnipresent³¹ and it is therefore especially difficult to distinguished between a glacial mound (*ang.* drumlins; *ger.* der Drumlin; *slo.* kopaste morene) and a burial mound. This has been already discussed by S. Gabrovec and J. Pečnik in excavation reports of the site Bled-Žale.³² S. Gabrovec clearly concludes that here we are only dealing with glacial mounds.³³ However, the existence of the Iron Age³⁴ and Early Medieval graves³⁵ at the top of a glacial mound (3-4m high) have been documented at the site Bled-Žale.³⁶ The use of glacial mound as burial mound has been also documented for Early Roman Period at the Zasipl³⁷ and for the Early Medieval Period at the site Bodešče³⁸ where oldest grave of the founder of the family (grave 43) was located at top a moraine.³⁹ Another likely interpretation of numerous low mounds (high 0.3m-0.5m) is that these are clearance cairn - an irregular and unstructured collection of fieldstones which have been removed from arable land or pasture to allow for more effective agriculture (ID 22-23). Late medieval pottery rim has been discovered (ID 24) on the path leading from the village Jermanka to the Bled-Dobe confirming the usage of this area in medieval period.

²⁹ Terminal moraine is made up of a ridge-like accumulation of debris deposited at the snout of the glacier (Miaschi 2017).

³⁰ Novak & Bavec 2013, 29; Melnik 1929/30, Priloga 1.

³¹ Novak & Bavec 2013, 29.

³² Gabrovec 1960, 9-10.

³³ Gabrovec 1960, 10.

³⁴ Gabrovec 1960, fig. 1, Tab. XL; Knific 1984, 101.

³⁵ Pleterski 2008, 33-39.

³⁶ EŠD 12077.

³⁷ An early Roman pot was found in a stone cemetery in Zasipl (after Pleterski A., Topographical Record, February 13, 1995, summarized by L. Lavrenčič).

³⁸ Pleterski 1982, 146; Pleterski 2013, 55.

³⁹ EŠD 13084.

Fig. 5: Bled-Žale. Glacial mound on which Iron Age graves were documented (Gabrovec 1960, Fig. 1, Tab. XL).

3.3 Zone 3 (Tuesday, 27. 08. 2019)

Description of the traces recorded on LiDAR. St. Katherine – Hom, Zasip (Fig. 6; 6a).

According to the archaeological reports at the top and on the south-eastern slope of the hill Hom traces of prehistoric settlements, cemetery⁴⁰ and anthropogenic terraces are present.⁴¹ At the foot of hill in the village Zasip multiperiodic (Iron Age, Antiquity and the early Middle Ages) settlement and burials and also the traces of Early Medieval field system could be recognized.⁴²

Here we have to deal with similar situations as in *zone 2*. Archaeological and geological features are closely interlaced and are very difficult to distinguish. On ALS data, numerous terraces are clearly visible on south-eastern slope of the hill Hom (834 m a.s.l). Also the sunken roads, that clearly cross-cut the terraces (ID 25-ID 26), are well preserved. Glacial

⁴⁰ The cemetery comprises the eastern extension of the hill Hom above Zasip and river Radovna, from the church of St. Catharine to the east and terraces to the southeast slope.

⁴¹ EŠD 13087.

⁴² EŠD 864.

mounds (perimeter 8-10m) and clearance cairn (high 0.3-0.5m) are present in the area (ID 27-29).

The glacial terraces have been documented by geologist (*Fig. 7*).⁴³ Terraces are running from east to west; approximal length ca. 450m, width 30m, high 1-2m; with a distinct slope facing south. Shorter ridges can be recognized on the eastern edge of the hill, with approximal length ca. 250m. Steep slope facing to the south and east have clearly visible narrow anthropogenic terraces (approximal length ca. 120-150m, width 2-5m, high 0.2-0.4m). However, the existence of settlement traces on ALS data could not be recognised. During the ground-truthing no artefacts have been detected.

Fig 7. The map of the hill Hom with glacial terraces, marked in black, by A. Melnik (Melnik 1929/30, Fig.1).

3.4 Zone 4 (Wednesday, 28. 08. 2019)

Description of the traces recorded on ALS. Mala Osojnica, Bled (*Fig. 8; 8a*).

Numerous features were recognised and recorded on small plateau of the hill Mala Osojnica (691 m a.s.l). During the construction work in Zaka, on eastern side of the hill, Bronze Age axe has been discovered.⁴⁴ This has led us to contemplate the possibility of existence of a (Bronze Age) settlement. Of particular interest was the feature consisted of three rectangular shapes (9 x9m) right in the southern edge of Mala Osojnica (ID 34-35). In this highly forested area we were mainly interested in, what it seemed to be, rectangularly shaped structures (ID 32, 33, 37; approximal length: 10-30m, width: 10-15 m). Sunken road is clearly visible on the ALS image area of the Zone 4 (*Fig. 8*). Road has been widened for the extraction of stone in a (Early Modern Period) quarry (ID 30-31). However, after the field assessment it was clear that these features are geological formations. The area is covered with

⁴³ Buser 1980, 34; Melnik 1929/1930, 12-13.

⁴⁴ EŠD 13082.

a (Triassic) dolomite.⁴⁵ As an additional argument we can add that the complete absence of artefacts leads to the same conclusion.

3.5 Zone 5 (Wednesday, 28. 08. 2019)

Description of the traces recorded on ALS. Jarše by Dindol (Fig. 9; 9a).

ALS image suggested existence of roughly rectangular shaped feature (dimensions: 100m x 110m). Even though this features could be recognised as possible remains of the land division i.e. field boundaries, seen on Franciscan cadastre (Fig. 10).⁴⁶ However, the existence of 1.- 2. century *villa rustica* with similar dimension (110m x 120m) on the other side of the Sava river at the Rodine⁴⁷ was good argument for the ground-check. The villa discovered at the Rodine has rectangular floor plan and it was surrounded by double walls.⁴⁸ Remains of a Roman Period settlements and building are known at nearby locations Velika Blata⁴⁹, Dobravce⁵⁰, and Žaleče.⁵¹ There are also traces of settlements in Želeče, Zasip, Pristava and Bohinjska Bela.⁵²

Although tempting to suggest this could represent a building it was equally possible that it is a geological feature. However, no artefacts have been found in the area including neighbouring ploughed field. Since Roman Period settlements are always accompanied with vast amounts of typical finds (e.g. *tegulae*, *amphorae*) we can conclusively argue that this location is not a Roman Period *villa rustica* site.

Fig 10: Map od Franciscan cadastre (left) with marked position of the features and ALS image on 0.5m DTM, SLRM visualisation.

⁴⁵ S. Buser & J. Cajhen 1978.

⁴⁶ Ribno (*Reifen*, SI AS 181/L224/g/CO2).

⁴⁷ The distance between locations is approx. 4 km.

⁴⁸ Valič, Petru 1964-65, 321-338.

⁴⁹ EŠD 30005.

⁵⁰ EŠD 29949.

⁵¹ EŠD 13072.

⁵² Knific 2008, 231-240.

4. Results

Results allow for a much firmer conclusion to be reached regarding the site distribution, settlement patterns and other features of ancient landscapes. In glacier landscapes such as Bled micro-region it is not always easy to distinguish between archaeological features and natural geological phenomena. For this a thorough knowledge of archaeology is required for any attempt to classify and date sites according their form. Remains of the last glaciation, such drumlins, moraines, periglacial processes shape landscape. These features are also omnipresent in excavation and prospection data and therefore have a pronounced impact on the archaeological interpretation. Since geomorphological process had strong impact to this region I would suggest cooperation with geologist. The geoarchaeological interpretation would enhance the understanding of this important region.

The results of archaeological survey that was carried out as part of the EMA-project is the discovery of new archaeological site located at the Ribenska gora. This site is preliminary dated to Prehistory and Late Antiquity Period and will added to an important dataset that can be integrated with remote-sensing approaches to contribute debates about settlement distributions in the Bled micro-region.

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5.3 Abbreviations

ARKAS: Arheološki kataster Slovenije (<https://iza2.zrc-sazu.si/>).

EŠD: Evidenčna Številka Dediščine / Unique Reference Number (Ministry of Culture, Republic of Slovenia, The Register of Slovene Cultural Heritage: <http://rkd.situla.org>).

ZBIVA: Zbiva v3.08 (<http://zbiva.zrc-sazu.si/>).

6. Figures and Photos

6.1 List of Figures

Fig. 1. The microregion of the Bled area with its soundings. 1m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 2. Interpreted as archaeological features (marked in red) with zones of interests.

Fig. 3. *Zone 1*. ALS image of archaeological site Ribenska gora (a) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 4. *Zone 2*. ALS image of Čisto polje (a) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; Simple local relief model (SLRM) visualisation.

Fig. 5. Bled-Žale. Glacial mound on which Iron Age graves were documented (Gabrovec 1960, Fig. 1, Tab. XL).

Fig. 6. *Zone 3*. ALS image of sv. Katarina above Zasip (a) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 7. The map of the hill Hom with glacial terraces (Melnik 1929/30, Fig.1).

Fig. 8. *Zone 4*. ALS image Mala Osojnica with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 9. *Zone 5*. ALS image of Jarše (Dindol) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; Simple local relief model (SLRM) visualisation.

Fig. 10. *Zone 5*. Map od Franciscan cadastre (left) with marked position of the features and ALS image on 0.5m DTM, SLRM visualisation.

6.2 List of Photos

Zone 1. ID 1 (path), ID 2 (path), ID 3 (find spot of stone block), ID 4 (path around tower), ID 5 (tower), ID 6 (find spot of pottery), ID 7 (terrace), ID 8 (terrace), ID 9 (find spot of pottery), ID 10 (possible building), OD 11 (terrace), ID 12 (terrace), ID 13 (possible quarry), ID 14 (prehistoric pottery); *Zone 2*. ID 15 (feature cut by modern path), ID 16 (the detailed photo of feature's consistency), ID 17-21 (feature visible on the field), ID 22-23 (clearance cairns), ID 24 (the late medieval pottery rim, identified by B. Štular); *Zone 3*. ID 25-26 (the road cross-cut the glacial terrace), ID 28-29 (clearance cairns); *Zone 4*. ID 30-31 (road along quarry face), ID 32 (features ridge); ID 33-36 (features ridges), ID 37 (features ridges); *Zone 5*. ID 38 (Jarše, with visible terrain inclination).

Photographer: Benjamin Štular, Edisa Lozić.

6.3 List of Attachments

Attachment 1: List of records of individual features.

Fig. 1. The microregion of the Bled area with its soundings. 1m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 2. Interpreted as archaeological features (marked in red) with zones of interests.

Fig. 3. *Zone 1*. ALS image of archaeological site Ribenska gora (a) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 4. Zone 2. ALS image of Čisto polje (a) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; Simple local relief model (SLRM) visualisation.

Fig. 6. Zone 3. ALS image of sv. Katarina above Zasip (a) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 8. Zone 4. ALS image Mala Osojnica with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; SVF visualisation.

Fig. 9. Zone 5. ALS image of Jarše (Dindol) with marked archaeological features (b). 0.5m DTM; Simple local relief model (SLRM) visualisation.

Photos: *Zone 1.*

Photos: *Zone 2*.

Photos: *Zone 3.*

Photos: *Zone 4.*

Photos: *Zone 5.*

EMA Project

Attachment 1

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
1	E.L	16.8.	SVF	building	1	prehistory	2	Prehistoric settlement. Hillfort.	
2	E.L	19.8.	SVF	building	1	prehistory	2	Prehistoric settlement. Hillfort.	
3	E.L	19.8.	SVF	buliding	1	prehistory	2	Prehistoric settlement. Hillfort.	
4	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	prehistoric settlement area	1	prehistory	2	Hillfort.	
5	E.L	19.8.	SVF	building	1	prehistory	2	Prehistoric settlement. Hillfort.	
6	E.L	19.8.	SVF	building	1	prehistory	2	Prehistoric settlement. Hillfort.	
7	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building?	0	prehistory	0	hillfort?	
8	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building?	0	prehistory	2	Prehistoric settlement.	Bohinjska Bela, EŠD 13085
9	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building?	0	prehistory	0	Prehistoric settlement?	
10	E.L	19.8.	SVF	quarry	0	unknown	0	quarry	
11	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	road	0	0	0	road to quarry	probably not modern
12	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	mound	1	prehistory	2	prehistoric mounds?	EŠD 13087
13	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
14	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	mound	2	prehistory	2	prehistoric mounds?	EŠD 13087
15	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	terrace	2	2	0	prehistoric terraces	EŠD13087
16	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	quarry	3	0	0	quarry	quarry
17	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	pits	0	0	0	prehistoric mining?	
18	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	earthwork	0	0	0	roman?	
19	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building	3	roman	3	Villa rustica	EŠD5298
20	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building	3	roman	0	Roman villa?	
21	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	quarry	3	roman	1	roman quarry?	
22	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building?	0	unknown	0	unknown	

EMA Project

Attachment 1

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
23	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	building	1	prehistory	1	prehistoric settlement?	
24	E.L.	19.8.	SVF	settlement	1	prehistory	1	prehistoric settlement	
25	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	earthwork ?	0	unknown	0	unknown	
26	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	unknown	2	unkown	0	unknown	
27	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	building, field boundary	2	unknown	0	modern?	
28	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	unknown, building?	2	unkown	0	unknown	
29	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	building?	2	unkown	0	unkown	
30	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	round feature	0	unknown	0	unknown	
31	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	3	unkown	0	holloway	
32	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
33	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
34	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
35	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
36	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
37	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
38	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
39	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
40	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
41	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
42	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
43	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
44	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
45	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
46	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
47	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
48	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
49	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
50	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
51	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
52	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
53	E.L.	20.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
54	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
55	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
56	E.L.	24.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
57	E.L.	24.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
58	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
59	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
60	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
61	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
62	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
63	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
64	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
65	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
66	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
67	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
68	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
69	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
70	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
71	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
72	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
73	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
74	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
75	E.L.	24.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
76	E.L.	24.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
77	E.L.	24.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
78	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
79	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
80	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
81	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
82	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
83	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
84	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
85	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
86	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
87	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
88	E.L.	24.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
89	E.L.	16.8.	SLRM	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
90	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
91	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
92	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
93	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
94	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
95	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
96	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
97	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
98	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
99	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
100	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
101	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
102	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
103	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
104	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
105	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
106	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
107	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
108	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
109	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
110	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
111	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
112	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
113	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
114	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
115	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
116	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
117	E.L.	16.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
118	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
119	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
120	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
121	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
122	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
123	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
124	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
125	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
126	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
127	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
128	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
129	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
130	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
131	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
132	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

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No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
133	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
134	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
135	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
136	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
137	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
138	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
139	E.L.	15.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
140	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
141	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
142	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
143	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
144	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
145	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
146	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
147	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
148	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
149	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
150	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
151	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
152	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
153	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
154	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
155	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
156	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
157	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
158	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
159	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
160	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
161	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
162	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
163	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
164	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
165	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
166	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
167	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
168	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
169	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
170	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
171	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
172	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
173	E.L.	14.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
174	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
175	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
176	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
177	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
178	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
179	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
180	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
181	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
182	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	unkown	
183	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
184	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
185	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
186	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
187	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
188	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
189	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
190	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
191	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
192	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
193	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
194	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
195	E.L.	13.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
196	E.L.	13.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
197	E.L.	13.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
198	E.L.	13.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
199	E.L.	13.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
200	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
201	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
202	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
203	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
204	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
205	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	line	0	unknown	0	unkown	
206	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
207	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
208	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
209	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
210	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
211	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
212	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
213	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
214	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
215	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
216	E.L.	12.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
217	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	0	unkown	0	quarry	
218	E.L.	22.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
219	E.L.	22.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
220	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
221	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
222	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
223	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
224	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
225	E.L.	22.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
226	E.L.	22.8.	OPEN	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
227	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	0	unknown	0	quarry	
228	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	0	unkown	0	quarry	
229	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
230	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
231	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
232	E.L.	22.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
233	E.L.	22.8.	SLRM	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
234	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
235	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
236	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	limekiln	2	modern	0	lime kiln?	
237	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	lime kiln	2	modern?	0	lime kiln?	
238	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	lime kiln?	2	modern?	0	lime kiln	
239	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	3	modern	0	quarry	
240	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
241	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
242	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	2	modern?	0	quarry?	

No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
243	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	3	modern?	0	quarry	
244	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	quarry	0	modern?	0	quarry	
245	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
246	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
247	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	building	2	unkown	0	building	
248	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
249	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	unkown	0	unkown	0	unkown	
250	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	building	0	unkown	0	building?	
251	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	unkown	0	unkown	0	unkown	
252	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
253	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	holloway	0	unkown	0	holloway	
254	E.L.	22.8.	SVF	lime kiln	2	modern?	0	lime kiln	
255	E.L.	22.8.	OPEN	holloway	1	moden?	0	holloway?, slipway?	
256	E.L.	22.8.	OPEN	slipway?	0	unkown	0	slipway?	
257	E.L.	22.8.	SLRM	building?	2	unkown	0	building?	
258	E.L.	22.8.	SLRM	unkown	1	unkown	0	unkown, roman camp?	
259	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	unkown	0	unkown	0	unkown	
260	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	unkown	2	unkown	0	unkown	
261	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	building	2	unkown	0	building?	
262	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	unkown	2	unkown	0	unkown	
263	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	unkown	0	unkown	0	unkown	
264	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	unkown	0	unkown	0	unkown	

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No.	Author	Date (2019)	Source	Feature Type	Confidence in Feature (1-3)	Chronology	Confidence in Chronology (1-3)	Interpretation	Varia
265	E.L.	23.8.	SLRM	building?	2	unkown	0	unkown	